

Modulatory effect of aqueous leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* on dyslipidemia in alloxan induced diabetic rats

Ezekiel E. Ben *, Asuquo E. Asuquo and Comfort O. Umoh

Department of physiology, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(02), 647–659

Publication history: Received on 02 January 2024; revised on 09 February 2024; accepted on 11 February 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.2.0337>

Abstract

Dyslipidemia is a major cause of cardiovascular complications in diabetes mellitus. This study was carried out to evaluate the modulatory effect of *Terminalia catappa* leaf extract on dyslipidemia in diabetic rats. Twenty-five (25) male wistar rats weighting 150-200 g were divided randomly into five groups with five rats each for the study. Group 1 was control administered 5 ml/kg body weight of distilled water orally. Group 2 was treated with aqueous leaf extract of *T. catappa* at 130 mg/kg body weight orally while Group 3 was diabetic group orally administered with distilled water, 5ml/kg body weight. Groups 4 and 5 were diabetic rats treated respectively with 130 mg/kg body weight of aqueous leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* and subcutaneous administration of insulin, 0.75 U/Kg body weight. Diabetes was induced with alloxan; 150 mg/kg body weight. The results showed significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in TC, TG, HDL, LDL and VLDL in diabetic untreated group. These were all reduced significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the *Terminalia catappa* leaf extract treated group. There was significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in Fasting blood glucose and increase in insulin levels. These changes were observed to be similar in diabetic insulin administered group. Therefore, the aqueous leaf extract of *T. catappa* modulates hyperglycemia induced dyslipidemia suggesting its potency in managing dyslipidemia in type 1 diabetes mellitus and may be used to ameliorate diabetes associated cardiovascular complications.

Keywords: Dyslipidemia; *Terminalia catappa*; Insulin; Cardiovascular Complication; Diabetes Mellitus.

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder considered as a growing non-infectious worldwide health challenge [1] in both developed and developing countries. It is specially characterized by hyperglycaemia due to defective insulin secretion, inaction or both [2]. This consequently leads to increased hepatic glucose production [3,4]. The complications of diabetes mellitus are associated with numerous hyperglycemia related injuries. There is an increased prevalence of DM globally with a projection of 500 million adults to be affected with diabetes mellitus by 2030 [5]. The risk of developing cardiovascular disease (CVD) is high in diabetic individuals [6] and CVD is the primary cause of death in people with either type 1 or type 2 diabetes [7,8]. It is reported that, CVD accounts for the high health care demand and expenditures in people with diabetes. [8,9]. Diabetes mellitus is associated with atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases (ASCVD) complications. Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease composes of coronary heart disease (CHD) [10,11], myocardial infarction [12], cerebrovascular disease and peripheral arterial disease with atherosclerotic origin [13]. The ASCVD constitutes the leading cause of morbidity and mortality for individuals with diabetes [13]. The increased risk of ASCVD stimulates aggressive investigation for therapeutic regimes that can achieve prevention of these complications [8].

* Corresponding author: Ezekiel E. Ben; Email: adoopraise@yahoo.com

Targeting of blood lipid concentration in diabetes becomes necessary. Studies have shown that lipid-lowering agents such as statins and fibric acid derivative decreases macrovascular disease in patients with diabetes mellitus [14]. These drugs are effective for both primary and secondary prevention of CVD [15]. Several studies have shown the efficacy of controlling individual cardiovascular risk factors in preventing or slowing ASCVD in people with diabetes. It has been advocated that natural medicinal substances be investigated with the aim of discovering alternative pattern of treatment by WHO [16]. This study seeks to evaluate the potentials of *Terminalia catappa* leaf extract on diabetic dyslipidemia in alloxan induced diabetes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of Plant Extract

Fresh leaves of *Terminalia catappa* were collected at the premises of the University of Uyo and the area was free of pesticides and other contaminants. The leaves were authenticated by a botanist at the Department of Botany and Ecological studies, University of Uyo and with herbarium number UUPH 22(a). The leaves were then washed with clean water to remove debris. The water was blotted out and kept overnight at room temperature to dry up. The clean leaves were pulverized and 5000 g of the pulverized leaves were soaked in 5 litres of deionised water for 18 hours. The mixture was filtered using muslin cloth and evaporated to dryness using thermostatic water bath at 45 °C until a semi solid paste of 204.18 g of the extract was obtained after evaporation representing a percentage yield of 4.08 %. The extract was stored in refrigerator for later use.

2.2. Preparation of Experimental Animal

Healthy adult male albino Wister rats weighting between 150-200 g were used for the study. The animals were procured from the animal house, Department of Physiology, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Uyo. The animals were housed in a well-ventilated cage in the animal house and they were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks and maintained in a 24-hour dark and light cycle. The animals were fed with standard pellets (from Guinea Feeds, Plc Nigeria) and have access to water *ad libitum*.

2.3. Induction of diabetes

Diabetes was induced by intraperitoneal injection of alloxan monohydrate at a dose of 150 mg/Kg body weight [17,18,19]. The animals were assessed for development of diabetes after 72 hours [20] by obtaining blood sample from the tip of the tail. The blood sample was dropped into glucose strip to measure the glucose level using a glucometer (One Touch Ultra, Life Scan Inc, U.S.A). Blood glucose of ≥ 200 mg/dl was considered diabetic (normal range of blood glucose in rat is 80 – 120mg/dl) and were used for the experiments [18,20]

2.4. Experimental Design

The experimental animals were randomly distributed into five (5) groups of five (n=5) rats per group as follows:

- **Group 1:** Control group administered with only distilled water orally at a dose of 5 ml/kg body weight.
- **Group 2:** Normal rats with only aqueous leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* at a dose of 130 mg/kg body weight administered orally.
- **Group 3:** Diabetic group administered with only distilled water orally at a dose of 5 ml/Kg body weight.
- **Group 4:** Diabetic group treated with *Terminalia catappa* leaf extract at a dose of 130 mg/Kg body weight by oral administration.
- **Group 5:** Diabetic group treated with exogenous Insulin at a dose of 0.75 U/Kg body weight by subcutaneous administration.

2.5. Determination of lipid profile

The total cholesterol, triglyceride and high-density lipoprotein was estimated by spectrophotometric method using standard analysis kits by Biotech (China) following the manufacturer's procedures. 1.0ml of reagent was prepared into all sample tubes labelled blank, standard, control and samples and pre-warmed at 37 °C for at least 2 minutes. 10ul of samples were added to respective tubes and mixed. The mixture was incubated for 10minutes at 37 °C and the absorbance was read at 520 nm. Low density lipoprotein and very low-density lipoprotein were determined by calculation using a mathematical formula by Friedewald et al [21] as follows;

Low density Lipoprotein (LDL, mg/dL) = Total cholesterol (TC, mg/dL) –High density Lipoprotein (HDL) mg/dL

2.6. Very low-density Lipoprotein (VLDL, mg/dL) = Triglyceride (TG)/5 mg/dL.

Assessment of Cardiovascular Risk Indices in Normal and Diabetic groups

Cardiovascular risk of the *T. catappa* was calculated using various indices to assess the cardiovascular disease index and coronary heart disease index.

(a) Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP) was calculated as:

$$\text{AIP} = \text{Log} (\text{TG}/\text{HDL-c})$$

(b). Castelli's risk Index-I (CRI-I) and Castelli's Index-II (CRI-II) were calculated as follows:

$$\text{CRI-I} = \text{TC}/\text{HDL-c} \text{ and } \text{CRI-II} = \text{LDL-c}/\text{HDL-c}$$

where: TG is Triglyceride, HDL-c is High density lipoprotein-cholesterol, LDL- c is Low density lipoprotein-cholesterol and TC is Total cholesterol

2.7. Measurement of fasting blood glucose

Fasting blood glucose (FBG) was measured in the animals after overnight fast (about 14 hours) and the blood sample was obtained by pricking the tip of the tail. Measurement of blood glucose was done using glucometer (One Touch, Life Scan USA) on day 1, 4 and 14 [22].

2.8. Determination of serum insulin level

Serum insulin level was analysed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method. Commercial analysis kits for rat insulin (Biotech, China) was used following the manufacture's procedure. The absorbance or optical density was obtained at 450 nm using a microtiter plate reader

2.9. Statistical analysis

The data obtained from the result was subjected to statistical testing using GraphPad Prism 5.0 software. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with post hoc Turkey test was carried out. The result was presented as mean + standard error of mean (SEM) and the values with $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

3. Results

3.1. Serum Total Cholesterol (TC) level

Figure 1 Serum Total cholesterol levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group, c= test vs diabetic+extract.

The results of Total cholesterol are represented in figure 1. The serum total cholesterol level was 28.80 ± 1.43 mg/dl in the control group, 58.20 ± 2.29 mg/dl in control+extract group and 107.0 ± 3.11 mg/dl in diabetic group. The diabetic group presented with a significantly ($p < 0.05$) raised TC level compared with the control group. The TC level was seen to reduce significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the diabetic+extract group to a mean value of 80.80 ± 1.96 mg/dl compared with the diabetic group but this value was still higher than the control group value. In diabetic insulin treated group, there was also a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction to mean value of 70.40 ± 1.83 mg/dl when compared with diabetic group but not with the control group.

3.2. Serum Triglyceride (TG) Level

The results of Triglyceride (TG) are represented in figure 2. The value of triglyceride in the control group was 23.00 ± 1.05 mg/dl, the control+extract was 29.20 ± 1.46 mg/dl while diabetic group was 65.40 ± 2.68 mg/dl. the TG of the diabetic group was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than the control group. The diabetic group treated with *T. catappa* leaf extract and insulin showed significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction to a mean value of 46.40 ± 2.21 mg/dl and 47.0 ± 3.03 mg/dl respectively when compared with diabetic group but was however significantly higher than the control group value.

Figure 2 Serum Triglyceride levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group.

3.3. Serum High Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (HDL-c) Level

Figure 3 Serum High density lipoprotein-cholesterol levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group.

In figure 3, the results of high-density lipoprotein (HDL-c) are represented. The serum levels of HDL for control, control+extract and diabetic groups were 38.40 ± 2.54 mg/dl, 33.80 ± 0.80 mg/dl and 86.60 ± 3.23 mg/dl respectively. Comparing the results, the HDL-c of diabetic group was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than the control group while the control+extract group showed no significant change on the HDL-c. The HDL-c in diabetic group treated with extract was 44.20 ± 0.49 mg/dl and insulin treated group was 52.80 ± 3.56 mg/dl. The observed reductions were significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared with the diabetic group but not the control group.

3.4. Serum Low Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (LDL-C) Level

The results of Low-density lipoprotein are represented in figure 4. The serum low density lipoprotein level was 55.60 ± 1.97 mg/dl in the control group, 71.00 ± 2.95 mg/dl in control+extract group and 141.60 ± 4.01 mg/dl in diabetic group. But in diabetic group treated with extract, the value significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced to 64.00 ± 2.45 compared to the diabetic group although it was still higher than the control group value. Diabetic+insulin group also showed significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction to mean value of 59.80 ± 0.92 mg/dl.

Figure 4 Serum Low density lipoprotein-cholesterol levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group.

3.5. Serum Very Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (VLDL-C) Level

Figure 5 Serum Very low density lipoprotein-cholesterol levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group.

The results of very low-density lipoproteins are represented in figure 5. The serum level of very low-density lipoprotein was 4.60 ± 0.27 mg/dl in the control group, 5.84 ± 0.41 mg/dl in control+extract group and 13.08 ± 0.54 mg/dl in diabetic group. The diabetic+extract and diabetic+insulin groups showed significant ($p < 0.05$) reductions to mean values of 9.28 ± 0.44 mg/dl and 9.40 ± 0.61 mg/dl respectively compared to the diabetic group. These were higher than the control group value.

3.6. Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG) Level on Different Days

The results of the fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels in different days within the group is presented in table 1. The result in control group showed slight changes on day 1, 4 and 14 which had no significant difference within the days. But there was significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction on day 4 FBG in control+extract group when compared with its day 1 and this may be attributed to the effect of the extract. In the diabetic group, the glucose level significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased on day 4 and 14 respectively compared with day 1 and this was attributed to the alloxan effect. Groups administered with extract and insulin showed significant ($p < 0.05$) reductions on day 14 compared to their respective values on day 4 after diabetes induction.

Moreover, the fasting blood glucose level across all the groups on different days are shown in figures 6a, 6b and 6c. The FBG on day 1 in all the groups were not different significantly. Day 4 showed significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the diabetic induced groups (diabetic group, diabetic+extract group, diabetic+insulin group) compared with day 4 glucose level in control group. On day 14 there was significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in FBG levels of extract and insulin treated groups (diabetic+extract and diabetic+insulin) compared with diabetic group but significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than control group.

Table 1 Changes on Fasting Glucose Level between days in each group

GROUPS	FASTING BLOOD GLUCOSE (g/ml)			% Relative Change from	
	Day 1	Day 4	Day 14	Day 1-4	Day 4-14
Control	59.3 ± 9.9	68.3 ± 5.7	86.3 ± 3.95	-15.2	-26.4
Non-diabetic+ Extract	61.4 ± 2.6	50.4 ± 2.4^a	59.6 ± 2.54	+17.9	-18.3
Diabetic Control	52.2 ± 7.2	216.6 ± 11.4^a	264.6 ± 5.9^a	-314.9	-22.2
Diabetic + Extract	42.8 ± 4.2	295.0 ± 31.9^a	104.4 ± 2.3^{ab}	-589.3	+64.6
Diabetic + Insulin	44.5 ± 1.8^b	303.0 ± 14.5^a	139.8 ± 5.7^{ab}	-603.4	+57.2

N= 5; a Significant change compared to day 1 ($p < 0.05$); b Significant change compared to day 4 ($p < 0.05$)

Figure 6a Day 1 fasting blood glucose levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$.
 *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract.

Figure 6b Day 4 fasting blood glucose levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group.

Figure 6c Day 14 fasting blood glucose levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group.

3.7. Serum Insulin level in diabetic and non-diabetic groups

Figure 7 Serum insulin levels in normal and diabetic treated groups. Values are in mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$. *= test vs control, a= test vs control+extract, b= test vs diabetic group, c= test vs diabetic+extract.

The changes in the serum levels of insulin is represented in figure 7. The result showed that control group had insulin level of 4.20 ± 0.22 U/mL and a slight increase in control+extract group to 4.49 ± 0.11 U/mL. The insulin level decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) to mean value of 0.68 ± 0.6 U/mL in the diabetic group compared with control. In the diabetic treated with extract, there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in serum insulin level up to 1.72 ± 0.06 U/mL compared with diabetic group. This value was however significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than the control group. Similarly, the insulin treated diabetic group had insulin level of 4.63 ± 0.018 U/mL which was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased when compared with diabetic group and diabetic+extract groups but marginally higher than the value of the control group.

3.8. Cardiovascular risk assessment

The cardiovascular risk assessment was calculated using Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP) and Castelli's Index 1 and 2 (CRI-I & CRI-II) as represented in table 2. The results showed that extract treated groups had low values of AIP compared with the control and diabetic groups. On the other hand, the CRI-I value was higher in extract treated groups compared to control and diabetic groups but the CRI-II was higher in control+extract treated group but reduced in diabetic group treated with the extract.

Table 2 Assessment of Cardiovascular Risk Indices in Normal and Diabetic groups

Risk Indices	Control	Control + Extract	Diabetic	Diabetic + Extract	Diabetic + Insulin
AIP	-0.22	-0.06	-0.12	-0.04	-0.05
CRI-I	0.78	1.72	1.24	1.83	1.33
CRI-II	1.45	2.1	1.64	1.45	1.13

AIP: Atherogenic Index of Plasma, CRI-I: Castelli's Risk Index-1, CRI-II: Castelli's Risk Index-II

4. Discussion

Dyslipidaemia is one of the common abnormalities associated with diabetes mellitus [23,24,25]. Primary therapeutic target for diabetes mellitus is to achieve tight glycaemic control. This however may not achieve total correction of the changes in lipid status and its related effects [26]. Therefore, adjunct therapy has been advocated in managing diabetes to address both glycaemic and lipidemic status to forestall some associated cardiovascular disorders [23]. This study was carried out to evaluate the modulating effect of aqueous leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* on dyslipidemia in diabetic rats. The result of lipid profile showed that total cholesterol (TC), triglyceride (TG), high density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-c), low density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-c) and very low density lipoprotein-cholesterol (VLDL-c) were increased significantly in the diabetic untreated group compared with the control group. The results of TC and TG agrees with previous reports by other researchers associating diabetes mellitus with increased synthesis of cholesterol [27,28] and increased triglyceride [29,27,28]. This may be due to higher rate of hepatic production of cholesterol and triglyceride rich VLDL-c [30] and decreased removal of TG by peripheral tissues such as adipose tissues and muscles [31]. In diabetes mellitus, the inability of the cells to take up glucose affects the cellular energy metabolism [32] and changes in triglyceride is associated with changes in energy metabolism. Insulin deficiency leads to high TG production as well as inability of the body to utilize triglyceride for energy [33]. It is reported that high TG level has strong association with inadequate glycaemic control in humans [34] and complex relationship between TG and glucose metabolism may be influenced by antidiabetic drugs such as insulin and metformin [35]. The result showed that insulin treated group TG significantly decrease compared with the untreated diabetic group. The chronic action of dyslipidemia is associated cardiovascular complications [36,37] while the glycaemic control constitutes the acute effect [38]. Therefore, handling of TG can invariably address both acute and chronic disorders. Comparing with diabetic group administered with leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa*, there was similar trend of reduction. It is speculated that atherogenic tendency of hypertriglyceridemia could be attenuated by treating of hypertriglyceridemia [39]. This reduction in hypertriglyceridemia following extract treatment can attenuate potential atherogenic tendency, improve insulin sensitivity, enhance glucose uptake and utilization by peripheral tissues.

Moreover, abnormal HDL-c metabolism as a risk factor in cardiovascular disorders have been established. Documented evidence had shown that HDL-cholesterol level is reduced in type 2 diabetes mellitus [40] but raised in type 1 diabetes mellitus [41]. It was observed that the HDL-c level was significantly increased in diabetic group compared with control group. This is contrary to the report of Pandhare et al [42] but corroborates with the findings of Gourgari et al [43], Orchard et al [41] and supported by research report of [44] that low HDL is not common in type I diabetes mellitus. High incidence of cardiovascular heart disease (CHD) reported in type 1 diabetes mellitus [45,46,47] is attributed to associated dyslipidemia [48,49,50] in which HDL-c have been implicated. It is generally known that HDL-c possesses a

cardioprotective potential cholesterol exchange capacity (CEC) through reverse transport of cholesterol from LDL-c to the liver for excretion [51,52] anti-inflammatory [53,54,55] and anti-oxidative functions [56,57]. Contrary to previous beliefs that increased HDL-c protect against cardiovascular disease, studies have shown that abnormally raised HDL-c does not protect against coronary heart disease (CHD) [58]. There is increasing evidence on failure of increased circulating HDL-c to protect against coronary heart disease [59,60]. Biological activities of HDL-c may be altered in various pathological conditions resulting in loss of protective properties. In a poorly controlled diabetes, hyperglycemia induced covalent modification of apolipoprotein major HDL particles such as apo-AI alters metabolism and functions of HDL-c [61,62,63]. Following increased oxidative stress, glycoxidation of HDL proteins [64,65] and peroxidation of HDL lipid [66] occur. Since the functionality of HDL-c can be affected in diseased condition like diabetes mellitus, the increased level of HDL-c may indicate abnormalities associated with HDL-c sub-fractions, protein contents or size [67]. Such alterations in HDL-c protein content results in a dysfunctionality of HDL-c particles and reduces the protecting capability against cardiovascular disease. The observed reduction of HDL-c level towards the control value by extract of *Terminalia catappa* on HDL-c was considered beneficial. It is reported that some affected HDL-c protein may be corrected by obtaining good glycemic control while some proteins are not. Thus, the use of therapeutic agent capable of modulating the HDL-c proteins becomes necessary option to enhance the cardioprotective function of HDL-c. Therefore, the leaf extract of *Terminalia catappa* modulates abnormal HDL-c changes in diabetes mellitus. Although there is need to evaluate the specific manner in which the HDL-c is affected by the extract, it could be speculated that the extract may interfere with changes in either the HDL-c sub-fractions or HDL-c protein content or improved cholesterol efflux capacity [63]. The reduction of HDL-c levels in extract and insulin treated groups were similar when compared with the diabetic untreated group but not as low as the control group.

Further more, raised LDL-cholesterol as cardiovascular risk is well established. In the diabetic untreated group, the level of LDL was significantly increased. The result is in line with many research reports [68,69] but does not agree with reports that LDL-c is normal in diabetic condition [49]. However, the administration of extract in diabetic+extract group reduced the LDL-c to level not different from control. The observed reduction is consistent with [70,71,72]. The importance of maintaining low LDL-c in diabetes mellitus have been stressed [73] because increased LDL-c is a major risk factor in development of atherosclerosis [74] and associated macrovascular complications in diabetes mellitus [75]. The result of this study implies that the extract of *T. catappa* leaves can reduce LDL-c in diabetes mellitus thus mitigating the process of developing atherosclerotic cardiovascular disorders (ASCVD). Assessing cardiovascular risk showed a reduced atherogenic index of plasma (AIP) in both normal and diabetic groups treated with aqueous extract of *T. catappa* compared with control and diabetic groups respectively. However, assessing coronary risk by Castelli's Risk Index (CRI-1 and CRI-11) reflects increased index value in extract treated nondiabetic and diabetic groups compared with control and non-treated diabetic group. This suggests the extract potency in reducing risk of developing cardiovascular disease (CVD) while prevention of coronary heart disease (CHD) may be questionable in diabetes mellitus and unattainable in non-diabetic state.

With regards to hyperglycemic control, fasting blood glucose in this study showed significant decrease in the extract treated group on day 14 compared with the fasting blood glucose on day 4 after alloxan administration in diabetic untreated, diabetic+extract and diabetic+insulin groups. Administration of insulin also significantly reduced the fasting blood glucose compared with the diabetic untreated group on day 14. The serum insulin level was significantly elevated in extract treated group though not as much as the elevation in insulin treated group. Research has reported that decrease in blood glucose is a major pathway in correcting dyslipidemia [76]. Therefore, the extract may function indirectly by its ability to improve glycemia and enhance insulin secretion as observed in this study. Therapeutically targeting dyslipidemia has been reported to be advantageous [77] and co-administration of lipid drugs had been recommended in the management regimes of diabetes mellitus. The observed extract anti-dyslipidemic function may be activated through pathways other than glycemic control and insulin secretion in the modulation of dyslipidemia.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the aqueous leaf extract of *T. catappa* modulates hyperglycemia induced dyslipidemia suggesting its potency in managing dyslipidemia in type 1 diabetes mellitus and may be used to ameliorate diabetes associated cardiovascular complications, hence possessing a cardioprotective function against atherosclerotic cardiovascular disorders in diabetic condition.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The experimental protocol received full ethical approval from Faculty Animal Research Ethics committee - Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences (FAREC-FBMS) with approval number 021PY30417

References

- [1] Maahs DM, Daniels SR, de Ferranti SD, Dichek HL, Flynn J, Goldstein BI, Kelly AS, Nadeau KJ, Martyn-Nemeth P, Osganian SK, et al. Cardiovascular disease risk factors in youth with diabetes mellitus: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. 2014;130(17):1532–58.
- [2] Galicia-Garcia U, Benito-Vicente A, Jebari S, Larrea-Sebal A, Siddiqi H, Uribe KB, Ostolaza H, and Martin C. Pathophysiology of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020; 21(17): 6275
- [3] Dabelea D, Staford JM, Mayer-Davis EJ, D’Agostino R Jr, Dolan L, Imperatore G, Linder B, Lawrence JM, Marcovina SM, Mottl AK, Association of type 1 diabetes vs type 2 diabetes diagnosed during childhood and adolescence with complications during teenage years and young adulthood. *JAMA*. 2017;317(8):825–35.
- [4] Gourgari E, Dabelea D, Rother K. Modifiable risk factors for cardiovascular disease in children with type 1 diabetes: can early intervention prevent future cardiovascular events? *Curr Diabetes Rep*. 2017;17(12):134.
- [5] Maahs DM, Maniatis AK, Nadeau K, Wadwa RP, McFann K, Klingensmith GJ. Total cholesterol and high-density lipoprotein levels in pediatric subjects with type 1 diabetes mellitus. *J Pediatr*. 2005;147(4):544–6.
- [6] Dal Canto E, Ceriello A, Ryden L, Ferrini M, Hansen TB, Schnell O, Standl E, Beulens JWJ. Diabetes as a cardiovascular risk factor: An overview of global trends of macro and micro vascular complications. *European Journal of Preventive Cardiology*. 2019; 26(2): 25-32
- [7] Diz AP, Carvajal-Rodriguez A, Skibinski DO. Multiple hypothesis testing in proteomics: a strategy for experimental work. *Mol Cell Proteom*. 2011;10(3):M110-004374.
- [8] Mi H, Muruganujan A, Casagrande JT, Thomas PD. Large-scale gene function analysis with the PANTHER classification system. *Nat Protoc*. 2013a;8(8):1551–66.
- [9] Mi H, Muruganujan A, Thomas PD. PANTHER in 2013: modeling the evolution of gene function, and other gene attributes, in the context of phylogenetic trees. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2013b; 41: D377–86.
- [10] Hovland A, Jonasson L, Garred P, Yndestad A, Aukrust P, Lappégard KT, Espevik T, Mollnes T. E. The complement system and toll-like receptors as integrated players in the pathophysiology of atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis*. 2015;241(2):480–94
- [11] Gordon SM, Remaley AT. High density lipoproteins are modulators of protease activity: implications in inflammation, complement activation, and atherothrombosis. *Atherosclerosis*. 2017; 259:104–13
- [12] Hertle E, van Greevenbroek MM, Stehouwer CD. Complement C3: an emerging risk factor in cardiometabolic disease. *Diabetologia*. 2012;55(4):881–4
- [13] Chertow B, Edwards JC. Advances in diabetes for millennium: Vitamins and oxidative stress in Diabetes and its complications. *Medscape General Medicine*, 6:1-10.
- [14] Alexopoulos AS, Qamar A, Hutchins K, Crowley MJ, Batch BC, Guyton JR. Triglycerides: emerging targets in diabetes care? Review of moderate hypertriglyceridemia in diabetes. *Curr Diabetes Rep*. 2019; 19-13.
- [15] Wang KL, Liu CJ, Chao TF. Risk of new-onset diabetes mellitus versus reduction in cardiovascular events with statin therapy. *Am J Cardiol*. 2014;113:631-636.
- [16] Shaito A, Thuan DT, Phu HT, Nguyen TH, Hasan H, Halabi S, Abdelhady S, Nasrallah GK, Eid AH & Pintus G. Herbal Medicine for Cardiovascular Disease: Efficacy, Mechanism, and Safety. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020; 11:422.
- [17] Katsumata K, Katsumata Y, Ozawa T, Katsumata J. Potentiating effect of combined usage of three sulfonylurea drugs on the occurrence of alloxan diabetes in rats. *Horm Metab Res*. 1993; 25:125-126.

- [18] Kulkarni S. Commonly used drugs, their doses and nature of action in laboratory animals. 3rd ed. Vallabh Prakashan Delhi: Hand book of Experimental Pharmacology. 2005;190-195.
- [19] Etuk, E. U. (2010). Animal model for studying diabetes. *Agriculture and Biology Journal of North America*, 1(2): 130 – 134.
- [20] Borgohain R, Lahon K, Das S, Gohain K. Evaluation of mechanism of anti-diabetic activity of Terminalia chebula on alloxan and adrenaline induced diabetic albino rats. *Int J Pharma Bio Sci.* 2012;3(3):256- 266.
- [21] Friedewald WT, Levy RT, Frederickson DS. Estimation of the concentration of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in plasma without use of the preparative ultracentrifuge. *Clin Chem*, 18:499-502
- [22] Ben EE, Ekaidem SI. Plasma insulin and working dynamics of calcium channel blockers on thyroid hormone impaired glucose metabolism. *British Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2016 13(5): 1-8
- [23] Kalofutis, C., Piperi C., Kalofutis A., Harris F., Phoenix D. and Singh J. Type II diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular risk factors current therapeutic approaches. *Exp Clin Cardiol.* 2007;12(1):1-17
- [24] American Diabetes Association (2017). Cardiovascular disease and risk management. *Diabetes Care*, 40 (suppl 1); 575 – 587.
- [25] Abdissa, D. and Hirpa, D. (2022). Dyslipidemia and its associated factors among adult diabetes outpatients in West Shewa zone public hospitals, Ethiopia. *BMC Cardiovascular Disorders*, 22 (39): 1 – 8.
- [26] Wang S, Ji X, Zhang Z, & Vue F. Relationship between lipid profiles and Glycemic control among Patients with type 2 Diabetes in Qingdao, China. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020; 17(15): 5317
- [27] Mona, HM, Sahar SA, Hend SM, Nanees AA. Dyslipidemia in type 1 diabetes mellitus: Relation to diabetes duration, glycemic control, body habitus, dietary intake and other epidemiological risk factors. *Egyptian Pediatric Association Gazzette.* 2015,63: 63-68
- [28] Alrasheed AA. Dyslipidemia among patients with type 1 Diabetes and its Associated Factors in Saudi Arabis: An analytical Cross Sectional Study. *Cureus.* 2022; 14(2) e21923
- [29] Ginsberg HN. Diabetic Dyslipidemia:Basic mechanisms underlying the common hypertriglyceridemia and low HDL cholesterol levels. *Diabetes.* 1996; 45(3)27-30
- [30] Bhagyashree K, Bhuyar K. Lipid profile in diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Biotechnology and Biochemistry.* 2017;123-131
- [31] Raz I, Eldor R, Cernea S, & Shafir E. Diabetes, insulin resistance and derangements in lipid metabolism. Cure through intervention in fat transport and storage. *Diabetes/metabolism research and reviews.* 2005; 21(1):3-14
- [32] McCall A. Glucose transport. 2019 Glucose transport. *Stress Physiology, Biochemistry and Pathology Academic press*, 293-307.
- [33] Chattanda S, Mgonda Y. Diabetic Dyslipidemia among Diabetic Patients Attending Specialized Clinics in Dar es Salaam. *Tanzania Medical Journal.* 2008; 23(1)
- [34] Zheng D, Dou J, Liu G, Pan Y, Yan Y, Liu F, Gaisano HY, Lu J, He Y. Association between triglyceride level and glycemic control among insulin-treated patients with type 2 diabetes. *The Journal of Clinical endocrinology and Metabolism.* 2019;104(4):1211-1220.
- [35] He L. Metformin and Systemic metabolism. *Trends pharmacol Sci.* 2020; 41(11): 868-881
- [36] Rubins, HB, Robins SJ, Collins D, Nelson DB, Elam MB, Schaefer EJ. Diabetes plasma insulin and cardiovascular disease. Subgroup analysis from the Department of Veterans Affairs High-density Lipoprotein Intervention Trial (VA-HIT). *Arch Intern Med.* 2002; 162: 2597-604
- [37] Miller M. Dyslipidemia and cardiovascular risk: the importance of early prevention. *QJM International Journal of Medicine.* 2009; 102(9): 657-667.
- [38] Tirosch A, Shai I, Bitzur R, Kochba I, Tekes-Manova D, Israeli E, Schochat T, Rudich A. Changes in triglyceride levels overtime and risk of type 2 diabetes in young Men. *Diabetes care.* 2008; 31(10): 2032-2037.
- [39] Steirner G, Lewis G. Triglyceride-Rich lipoprotein Metabolism in Diabetes. In Gallo, L. L. (eds) *Cardiovascular Disease. GWUMC Department of Biochemistry Annual Spring Symposia*, Springer, Boston, MA. Pp 49-55
- [40] Brunham LR, Kruit JK, Pape TD. Beta-cell ABCA1 influences insulin secretion, glucose homeostasis and response to thiazolidinedione treatment. *Natural Medicine.* 2007; 13:340–347.

- [41] Orchard TJ, Costacou T, Kretowski A, Nesto RW Type 1 diabetes and coronary artery disease. *Diabetes Care*. 2006; 29:2528–2538.
- [42] Pandhare RB, Sangameswaran B, Mohite PB, Khanage SG. Anti-hyperglycaemic and lipid lowering potential of *Adenanthera pavonina* Linn. In Streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Orient Pharm Exp Med*. 2012;12(3):197-203
- [43] Gourgari E, Ma J, Playford MP. Proteomic alterations of HDL in youth with type 1 diabetes and their associations with glycemic control: a case-control study. *Cardiovasc Diabetol*. 2019;18:43
- [44] Heier M, Borja MS, Brunborg C. Reduced HDL function in children and young adults with type 1 diabetes. *Cardiovasc Diabetol*. 2017;16:85
- [45] Nissen SE, Tardif JC, Nicholls SJ, Revkin JH, Shear CL, Duggan WT, Ruzyllo W, Bachinsky WB, Lasala GP, Tuzcu EM. ILLUSTRATE Investigators. Effect of torcetrapib on the progression of coronary atherosclerosis. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2007;356:1304–1316.
- [46] Schnell O, Cappuccio F, Genovese S. Type 1 diabetes and cardiovascular disease. *Cardiovasc Diabetol*. 2013;12:156
- [47] Colom C, Rull A, Sanchez-Quesada JL, Perez A. Cardiovascular disease in type 1 diabetes mellitus: Epidemiology and management of Cardiovascular risk. *J Clin. Med*. 2021;10(8):1798
- [48] Turner RC, Millns H, Neil HA, Stratton IM, Manley SE, Matthews DR, Holman RR. Risk factors for coronary artery disease in non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus: United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS: 23). *British Medical Journal*. 1998; 316:823–828.
- [49] Ginsberg HN, Elam MB, Lovato LC. ACCORD Study Group. Effects of combination lipid therapy in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *New England Journal Medicine*, 2010; 362: 1563–1574
- [50] Chapman MJ, Ginsberg HN, Amarenco P. Triglyceride-rich lipoproteins and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol in patients at high risk of cardiovascular disease: evidence and guidance for management. *European Heart Journal*. 2011 32:1345–1361
- [51] Hui N, Barter PJ, Ong KL, Rye KA. Altered HDL metabolism in metabolic disorders: insights into the therapeutic potential of HDL. *Clin Sci (Lond)* 2019; 133:2221–2235
- [52] Robert J, Osto E, von Eckardstein A. The endothelium is both a target and a barrier of HDL's protective functions. *Cells* 2021; 10:1041
- [53] Bonilha I, Zimetti F, Zanotti I. Dysfunctional high-density lipoproteins in type 2 diabetes mellitus: molecular mechanisms and therapeutic implications. *J Clin Med* 2021; 10:2233.
- [54] Florijn BW, Duijs JMGJ, Levels JH. Diabetic nephropathy alters the distribution of circulating angiogenic microRNAs among extracellular vesicles, HDL, and Ago-2. *Diabetes* 2019; 68:2287–2300.
- [55] He Y, Ronsein GE, Tang C. Diabetes impairs cellular cholesterol efflux from ABCA1 to small HDL particles. *Circ Res* 2020; 127:1198–1210.
- [56] Lui DTW, Cheung CL, Lee ACH. Carbamylated HDL and mortality outcomes in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2021; 44:804–809.
- [57] Cardner M, Yalcinkaya M, Goetze S. Structure-function relationships of HDL in diabetes and coronary heart disease. *JCI Insight* 2020; 5: e131491.
- [58] Schofield J, France M, Ammori B, Liu Y, Soran H. High density lipoprotein cholesterol raising: Does it matter? *Current Opinion in Cardiology*. 2013;28(3):464-474.
- [59] Briel M, Ferreira-Gonzalez I, You JJ, Karanickolas PJ, Akl EA, Wu P, Blechaz B, Bassler D, Wei X, Sharman A, Whitt I, Alves da Silva Khalid S, Nordmann Aj, Zhou Q, Walter SD, Vale N, Bhatnagar N, O'Regan O, Mills E, Bucher HC, Montori VM, Guyatt GH. Association between change in high density lipoprotein cholesterol and cardiovascular disease morbidity and mortality: Systematic review and meta-regression analysis. *Database of Abstracts of Review of Effects (DARE): Quality Assessed Reviews*. York, Centre for Reviews and Dissemination.
- [60] van der Steeg WA, Holme I, Boekholdt SM, Larsen ML, Lindahl C, Stroes ES, Tikkanen MJ, Wareham NJ, Faergeman O, Olsson AG, Pedersen TR, Khaw KT, Kastelein JJ High-density lipoprotein cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein particle size, and apolipoprotein A-1 significance for cardiovascular risk: the IDEAL and EPIC-Norfolk studies. *Journal of American College of Cardiology*. 2008; 51:634–642.

- [61] Ganjali, S, Dallinga-Thie GM, Simental-Mendia, LE. HDL functionality in Type I diabetes. *Atherosclerosis*. 2017;267: 99 - 109
- [62] Verges, B. Cardiovascular disease in type I diabetes: a review of epidemiological data and underlying mechanism. *Diabetes Metab*. 2020a; 46: 442 – 449.
- [63] Verges, B. Dyslipidemia in type I: a masked danger. *Trend Endocrinol Metab* . 2020b; 31: 422 – 434
- [64] Gordts SC, Singh N, Muthuramu I, De Geest B. Pleiotropic effects of HDL: towards new therapeutics areas for HDL-targeted interventions. *CurrMol Med*. 2014; 14(4) 481-503.
- [65] Chiesa ST, Charakida M. High-density lipoprotein function and dysfunction in health and disease. *Cardiovasc Drugs Ther*. 2019; 33(2): 207-219.
- [66] Mazzuferi G, Bacchetti T, Islam MO, Gianna F. High density lipoproteins and oxidative stress in breast cancer. *Lipids Health Dis*. 2021; 20: 143
- [67] Agoons D, Musani SK, Correa A, Golden SH, Bertoni AG, Echouffo-Tcheugui JB. High density lipoprotein and incident type 2 diabetes mellitus among African Americans: The Jackson Heart study. *Diabet Med*. 2022; 39(8): 14895
- [68] Kanrul-Hassa ABM, Alam SM, Zarin N, Kabir MA, Gaffar AJ, Hossan MF, Talukder SK, Raunak AIB, Nasu MMU, Asaduzzaman MD, Hasa MJ, Khan MAS, Selim S. Prevalence and patterns of dyslipidaemia among lipid lowering drug-naïve patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus – A country wide study in Bangladesh. *Endocrine and Metabolic Science*. 2023;13: 1-8s
- [69] Lee J, Lee Seung-Hwan. Lipid Variability in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Cardiovascular Prevention and Pharmacotherapy*. 2023; 5(4):126-133
- [70] Levy Y, Zaltsberg H, Ben Amotz A, Kanter Y, Aviriam M. Dietary supplement of a natural isomer mixture of beta-carotene inhibits oxidation of LDL derived from patients with diabetes mellitus. *Ann Nutr Metab*. 2000; 44: 54-60.
- [71] Andallu B, Vinay Kuma AV, Varadacharylu NC. Lipid abnormalities in Streptozotocin-diabetes: Amelioration by *Morus indica* L. cv *Suguna* leaves. *Int J Diabetes Dev Ctries*. 2009; 29(3): 123-128.
- [72] Bako Y, Mohammed JS, Waziri PM, Bulus T, Gwarzo MY, Zubabiru M. Lipid profile of alloxan induced diabetic wistar rats treated with methanolic extract of *Adansonia Digitata* fruit pulp. *Science World Journal*.2014; 9(2):19-24
- [73] Stark Casagrande S, Fradkin J, Sayday S, Rust K, Cowie C. The prevalence of meeting A1c, blood pressure and LDL goals among people with diabetes. *Diabetes care*. 2013; 36(8): 1988-2010
- [74] Wu D, Yang Q, Su, B, Hao J, Ma, H, Yuan W, Gao J, Ding F, Xu Y, Wang H, Zhao J, Li B. Low density lipoprotein cholesterol 4: The notable Risk factor for coronary heart disease development. *Front. Cardiovasc Med*. 2021; 8:1-11.
- [75] Rathsman B, Haas J, Persson M, Ludvigsson J, Svensson AM, Lind M, Andersson Franko M Nystrom T. LDL cholesterol level as a risk factor for retinopathy and nephropathy in children and adults with type 1 diabetes mellitus: A nationwide cohort study. *J Intern Med*. 2021; 289(6): 873-886.
- [76] Maahs Dm, Ogden LG, Dabelea D. Association of glycaemia with lipids in adults with type 1 diabetes: modification by dyslipidaemia medication. *Diabetologia*. 2010; 53:2518-2525.
- [77] Solano MP, Goldberg RB. Management of dyslipidemia in diabetes. *Cardiology in Review*, 2006; 14(3):125-135